

THE USE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING TO DIAGNOSE ILLNESSES OF THE BRAIN

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Abstract

Neurological illnesses affect more than twenty million people. People globally each year. Stroke, brain tumors, dementia, Parkinson's disease, and numerous other infections are examples of neurological conditions. Computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emissions tomography, and other standard diagnostics techniques are used. MRI has the best safety, highest detection rate, and consistency among these techniques. The benefits of non-invasive, non-radioactive, multi-parameter imaging offered by MRI as an advanced imaging technique make it a vital tool for identifying brain disorders. Perfusion-weighted imaging (PWI), diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) are the three subtypes of MRI. This research focuses on their technical tenets, traits, and clinical applications to further these three approaches—improving clinical neurological condition detection and therapy and developing magnetic resonance technologies.

Keywords: SPECT, Perfusion-Weighted Imaging (PWI), Diffuse Weighted Imaging (DWI), Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), And Brain Disorders Are Some Of The Terms Used In This Article.

INTRODUCTION

The brain is a vital organ of the human body, and brain lesions are extremely dangerous for people's health. Acute stroke, cerebral hemorrhage, brain abscess, brain tumor, Moyamoya disease, Alzheimer's disease, and others are examples of common brain disorders. Severe cases result in death, whereas mild ones might result in functional impairments such as limb, speech, and cognitive impairment. Therefore, prompt and accurate diagnosis and treatment are crucial for patients with brain illnesses. Techniques

traditionally used to diagnose brain diseases include computed tomography (CT), X-ray imaging, and others. However, these techniques have limitations, including low sensitivity, poor specificity, and sluggish imaging speed. Traditional approaches, for instance, have difficulty identifying minor hemorrhages and early strokes and cannot tell the difference between an early cerebral infarction and a transient ischemic attack (Chanu et al.,2023). The development of MRI as a compassionate and focused, quick diagnostic technique has coincided with the advancement of brain imaging studies. It is currently acknowledged as one of the most helpful brain imaging methods in therapeutic settings. A contrast of the imaging capabilities of X-ray, CT, PET, MRI, and the use of magnetic resonance angiography (MRA) for brain illnesses (Droby et al.,2023 and figure 1)

Figure 1: Comparative table of imaging methods for disorders of the cerebral cortex

A signal is produced by applying radiofrequency pulses in an external magnetic field using the spin properties of atomic nuclei within the human body in MRI, a biological imaging known as magnetic resonance imaging. Sectional images of the human body are displayed after the signal has been detected, analyzed, and utilized. MRI has a higher tissue picture resolution than CT and benefits from non-ionizing radiation. It can rely on numerous scan sequences to precisely look at brain tissue and assess the degree of damage it has sustained through cell windows, enabling clinicians to make a precise diagnosis as soon as possible and secure the best treatment option. (Qodarul et al.,2023)

Perfusion-weighted imaging (PWI), diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) are three of the most frequently employed MRI techniques in clinical practice. Among these, PWI can efficiently extract hemodynamic information by reflecting brain tissue's microvascular organization and blood flow perfusion.

For instance, PWI has clear benefits in assessing tumor grades and can better reflect pathological symptoms (Aldawsari et al., 2023). DWI is beneficial for diagnosing brain lesions because it can efficiently track their pathological and physiological status and reflect the micro-movement status of water molecules in living tissues (Zhu, 2023). For instance, Makita et al.'s research demonstrates that DWI has a diagnosis accuracy rate of up to 90% in patients with acute strokes, which is much greater than the 70% accuracy rate of conventional MRI and suggests a definite advantage. fMRI is one of the most helpful imaging techniques available for living things and is crucial for the early detection and treatment of traumatic brain injury. When diagnosing and treating brain diseases in clinical practice, it is advantageous to choose the proper imaging techniques based on the patient's condition in order to precisely show lesion data, such as its location, extent, and anatomy of the brain, shorten imaging and diagnostic times, reduce the likelihood of misdiagnosis, and give patients their time back. This article focuses on the features, benefits, and clinical uses of PWI, DWI, and fMRI to enhance the efficacy and security of therapy.

1. The use of PWI to diagnose illnesses of the brain

Perfusion supplies nearby tissues with oxygen and other materials carried by blood circulation through capillary networks and other exchange channels. Cerebral perfusion, frequently confused with blood flow, is the process by which blood crosses the blood-brain barrier to provide nutrients and oxygen to brain tissue.

PWI is a type of magnetic resonance imaging that reflects microvascular dispersion and tissue blood perfusion (Hsia, 2023). PWI quantifies hemodynamic data by identifying either endogenous or exogenous markers in the human body and is based on ultrafast MRI scanning and paramagnetic contrast agents.

PWI imaging techniques are often classified into two categories: endogenous indicator imaging methods and external indicator imaging methods. PWI has high consistency, high cost, and high spatial resolution. Arterial spin labeling (ASL), chemical exchange saturation transfer (CEST) approaches, and intravoxel incoherent motion (IVIM) are examples of endogenous imaging methods that use contrast chemicals.

These techniques use flowing blood as the contrast agent and use the proton spin motion in MR signals' inherent sensitivity to mark blood flow as an endogenous magnetic contrast agent. Dynamic sensitivity contrast MRI (DSC-MRI) and dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI) are examples of exogenous contrast imaging techniques separated into diffusive tracer and intravenous contrast material technology.

The former uses the paramagnetic antagonist Gd-DTPA, which has the benefit of a high signal-to-noise ratio, to indicate the substance in the blood flow without diffusing into the tissue (Liu, 2023). The latter measures the MR signal of non-proton nuclei by injecting exogenous markers into the body and letting them diffuse into the tissue. However, the proportion of signal to noise could be a lot higher. The main ideas behind these two strategies are shown in Figure 2 (Figure 2).

The capacity to quantify hemodynamic variables such as regional cerebral blood volume (rCBV), regional cerebral blood flow (rCBF), and regional mean transit time (rMTT) is a benefit of PWI technology. These criteria are essential for early detection and diagnosis of ischemic cerebrovascular illness. (Khalili e al., 2023)

Figure 2: Shows the distribution of CA in tissue, its interaction with water protons, and the resulting changes in the T1- or T2*-weighted signals that are caused

In clinical practice, PWI is crucial for identifying pathogenic abnormalities in the early stages of cerebral infarction. When the blood-brain barrier is unharmed, the DSC-MRI method works by injecting a magnetic contrast agent, often Gd-DTPA, and calculating perfusion parameters based on the potent T2* effect of the contrast agent.

In order to monitor the direction of flow and changes in the blood flow volume of the contrast substance in the blood and assess the state and perfusion of tissue blood flow, T2*-weighted images are used to obtain the concentration-time signal curve (Hnilicova et al., 2023) The foundation of DCE-MRI is T1-weighted imaging, as well as the metabolism and absorption of contrast agents following injection in the body.

It displays dynamic contrast ingredient changes between the target and background—tissue in the vicinity. DCE-MRI is utilized to acquire hemodynamic data and infer the microenvironment and metabolic status of the target location using medical imaging algorithms (Perez et al., 2023). Advantages of DSC-MRI and DCE-MRI include their non-invasiveness, lack of radiation, and excellent resolution.

Table 1 contrasts DSC-MRI with DCE-MRI's operating principles, display objects, application ranges, examination time, safety, Imaging Principles, Applications, and Quantification of Parameters

Table 1: Assessment between DSC-MRI and DCE-MRI

Aspect	DSE-MRI	DCE-MRI
Contrast Agent	Gadolinium-based contrast agent	Gadolinium-based contrast agent
Purpose	Perfusion imaging	Assessment of tissue perfusion
Imaging Principle	Measures signal loss due to contrast agent passage through vessels	Measures contrast agent uptake and distribution in tissues
Perfusion Information	Blood flow, volume, mean transit time	Blood vessel permeability, blood volume, extravascular extracellular space
Image Acquisition	Rapid T2*-weighted imaging	T1-weighted imaging
Applications	Stroke assessment, brain tumor grading	Tumor characterization, angiogenesis evaluation, vascular permeability assessment
Quantification of Parameters	Relative cerebral blood volume (rCBV), relative cerebral blood flow (rCBF), mean transit time (MTT)	Transfer constant (Ktrans), an initial area under the curve (Ia)
Display object	Hemodynamic variables	Organisational functioning and metabolism.
Application range	Many illnesses	Metabolism or neurological conditions
Examination time	30-60min	10-20min
safety	Damage to kidneys and medication sensitivities are dangers.	Generally safe

DSC-MRI is frequently used to identify ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke since it can assess local cerebral blood flow. Additionally, DSC-MRI can quantify the tumor's blood volume, blood flow velocity, and vascular shape, which aids in determining the tumor's malignancy and growth characteristics. Furthermore, DSC-MRI may distinguish between high-grade carcinoma pseudoprogression and return. (Wettersvik et al., 2023). Utilized to keep track of how well tumor treatments are working. The vascular morphology, blood flow rate, blood capacity, and tumor permeability can all be assessed by DCE-MRI. Clinical settings have seen much DCE-MRI research and applications for conditions like brain tumors, liver cancer, and cardiovascular disorders. DCE-MRI will be utilized more and more in clinical diagnosis and treatment as MRI technology continues to advance and grow. Additionally, PWI is very useful in determining the extent of cerebral ischemia in those with Moyamoya illness. A chronic, advancing cerebrovascular occlusive condition called Moyamoya disease can result in intracranial artery stenosis, local cerebral hypo perfusion, delayed perfusion, and, in extreme situations, cerebral ischemia and infarction. After cerebral infarction, variations in blood flow are semi-quantitatively examined. PWI can offer metrics like rCBV, rCBF, and rMTT, allowing for precisely identifying the blood supply condition in the infarcted area. As a result, PWI is useful for assessing cerebral ischemia in people with Moyamoya illness. (Islam et al., 2023).

2. DWI's use in identifying disorders of the brain

When referring to the microscopic motion of particles, such as molecules, from high-concentration areas to low-concentration regions, we use the term "diffusion," which characterizes the irregular random movement of molecules. It measures in mm^2/s . DWI is the only imaging technique that can now measure and image the diffusion of water molecules in vivo. It can detect cellular edema, representing the functional condition of brain cells, and its high signal indicates the constrained diffusion of water molecules in ischemic regions. DWI can image the information of water molecule diffusion in tissues using the echo planar imaging (EPI) technique. The diffusion rate of water molecules in tissues is determined via DWI by altering the gradient's magnitude and direction, offering a non-invasive way to measure the rate, also known as serving as the diffusion factor. The diffusion coefficient examines the small-scale movement, expansion, and vibration changes inside an organization. The apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC), which corresponds to the rate of water molecule reverse diffusion at each pixel in DWI pictures, is displayed using color coding. Therefore, DWI pictures can detect various aberrant tissue states, including stroke, spinal cord injury, tumors, and other diseases. Although DWI provides excellent spatial resolution, minor motion can seriously impede signal quality. The EPI pulse sequence, on the other hand, can eliminate motion artifacts by a significant amount and cut the imaging time to 30ms, hence improving the accuracy of measured MR diffusion coefficients (Agrawal et al., 2023)

DWI is frequently utilized in clinical settings to identify an ischemic stroke. Early stroke with ischemic attack causes ischemia and hypoxia in the brain tissue, which leads to an imbalance of intracellular sodium ions and water and a high osmotic pressure inside the cells. As a result, there is cytotoxic edema, restricted water molecule diffusion in the brain tissue, and bright, elevated signals on the DWI. The ADC value and signal intensity drop due to the reduction in diffusion brought on by the constriction of extracellular space. DWI can identify neuronal damage and cell death within minutes of ischemia, providing a crucial foundation for early diagnosis and treatment. Using DWI pictures, Doctors can assess nearby brain tissue's perfusion condition and the ischemic penumbra's size. This knowledge will be helpful to doctors. DWI is frequently utilized in clinical settings to identify ischemia lesions, predict patients' conditions and prognoses, and select the best treatments. Figure 3(Figure 3) compares DWI, ADC, T2WI, and FLAIR detection effects for a patient with an early stroke. While DWI and PWI can successfully identify hyperacute stroke, traditional MR techniques cannot assess the breadth and severity of acute stroke. By using PWI to obtain parameters like rCBV, rCBF, and rMTT, it is possible to accurately select the indications for thrombolytic treatments and create an individualized treatment plan by comparing the area of abnormal perfusion on PWI with the area of abnormal signal on DWI Options for therapy for stroke.

Figure 3

Figure 3: An example of an analogy between DWI, ADC, T2WI, and FLAIR in diagnosing early cerebral infarction [1]. The patient is a woman 86 years old, with a blood pressure of 190/124 mmHg, 30 minutes of consciousness, and no abnormalities in the head CT scan. 1a: DWI exhibits abnormally high signals in the base of the brain and left frontal lobe in a patchwork pattern. 1b: On the ADC, the lesion is seen as a low signal ($b=1000$). The brain's left hemisphere exhibits no aberrant signal in 1c: T2WI and 1d: FLAIR.

Additionally, DWI is selective in identifying brain abscesses because the abscess cavity manifests as an evident diffuse confined high signal. The term "brain abscess" describes the development of a local abscess in the brain tissue due to a brain infection. Bacterial, fungal, or viral infections are the most common causes of brain abscesses. These infections can result in tissue in the brain necrosis and degradation, raise intracranial pressure, and induce brain edema, neurological impairment, and even death. Headache, fever, vomiting, and problems with consciousness are typical symptoms. The treatment approach typically entails antibiotics and surgical procedures to alleviate symptoms, restore brain function, and avoid problems. To prevent serious repercussions, this disease needs to be treated right away. Brain abscesses showed up as a high signal on DWI in 2021, according to Prabhu et al., 2023. The pus cavity of a brain abscess is filled with a viscous fluid that is highly viscous due to numerous inflammatory cells, necrotic tissue, bacteria, protein secretions, and other things. Due to the pus's high viscosity, which prevents water molecules from diffusing freely, the DWI signal is strong, and the ADC value is low. It is easier to diagnose the condition since the high signal of a brain abscess on DWI is distinct from the apparent low signal of cystic degeneration and necrosis on DWI.

3. The use of fMRI in the detection of brain disorders

Using measures of brain circulation and digestion, FMRI may infer the anatomy and function of each part of the brain by observing blood flow and metabolism changes between different brain regions. It can precisely detect the targeted brain tissue and monitor physiological data quantitatively there. For instance, fMRI can assess the degree of damage to functional and structural brain regions and reveal changes in brain network structure when diagnosing brain injuries.

Blood oxygenation level-dependent (BOLD) functional MRI can identify blood flow variations caused explicitly by neuronal activity in each brain region. Enhanced blood flow results in enhanced BOLD signals, which are strongly tied to changes in the ratio of oxygenated to deoxygenated hemoglobin concentrations (Dias et al., 2023). fMRI offers a high spatial resolution, is non-invasive, non-radioactive, and has good reproducibility. The results of fMRI are also more reproducible when compared to those of other imaging methods like PET and SPECT, which makes it a crucial tool for investigating brain activity and conducting studies in neuroscience. However, the fundamental drawback of fMRI is its reduced temporal resolution because it takes many seconds to minutes (depending on the scanning apparatus and experimental methodologies) to see changes, which limits its capacity to identify brain activity in a brief period. (Zhu et al., 2023). The fMRI method, known as susceptible weighted imaging (SWI), leverages the variations in magnetic susceptibility between tissues to improve image contrast and highlight tissue features. For improved observation of tiny brain structures like cerebral tiny bleeds (CMBs), SWI uses the impact of iron elements in tissues to boost picture contrast. SWI can detect lesions like vascular tumors and provide richer networks of smaller and more precisely detailed blood vessels. This technique is crucial for diagnosing catastrophic brain injury (TBI) and has a greater detection rate for CMBs after TBI than CT and DWI. Patients with acute brain injury (TBI) frequently display pathological alterations in clinical practice, mainly in CMBs. As opposed to SWI is a more sophisticated method of imaging as opposed to conventional MRI and can enhance image contrast and sharpness. Diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), an fMRI method, measures the diffusion direction and velocity of water molecules within the tissue to represent the microstructure of the tissue. The direction, length, thickness, and shape of the white matter fibers can be shown, and this knowledge is used to research both the physiological and pathological functions of the nervous system. To determine the diffusion tensor of each voxel in DTI, diffusion coefficients are divided into three directions. The tissue's texture, direction, and connectivity can be quantitatively defined based on the diffusion tensor's primary direction and eigenvalues, and spatial interpolation can be used to determine the 3D distribution of connected fiber bundles. Fractional anisotropy (FA), mean diffusion coefficient, axial diffusivity, and DTI are among the evaluation metrics of radiation diffusivity. DTI is primarily utilized in clinical settings to assess the health of white matter fibers following traumatic brain damage. (Anand et al., 2023). In clinical use, the FA factor acquired by DTI is a crucial sign for determining the severity of brain white matter injury. It is conducive to identifying and managing this condition (Poirier et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION AND PROGNOSIS

MRI is a non-invasive method of diagnosis that offers benefits, including excellent resolution, multi-parameter imaging, multi-angle imaging, excellent security, and strong repeatability. PWI is particularly useful in assessing illnesses like stroke, tumors, and infections since it has outstanding consistency and spatial accuracy and may assist doctors in analyzing the blood oxygenation of organs or tissues. The benefit of DWI is

that it may produce high-resolution images that can be used to identify conditions, including tumors, infections, cerebrovascular accidents, and neurological diseases such as cerebellar ataxia and leukoencephalopathies. fMRI can help clinicians diagnose problems, including syncope, mental health issues, and cognitive diseases, by detecting blood perfusion in particular brain regions and tracking real-time brain function activity. MRI has several clear benefits. However, the equipment cost and ongoing maintenance and operating expenses are likewise quite significant.

Additionally, MRI scans take a long time—usually between 30 and an hour—which can be highly unpleasant to specific patients. MRI machines make much noise, which could distract patients and medical professionals. Using signal undersampling, deep learning algorithms and image reconstruction algorithms can be combined to recreate images, lowering scanning time without compromising imaging quality. Building open and compact MRI technology will also advance the field of MRI.

References

- 1) Chanu, M. M., Singh, N. H., Muppala, C., Prabu, R. T., Singh, N. P., & Thongam, K. (2023). Computer-aided detection and classification of brain tumors using YOLOv3 and deep learning. *Soft Computing*, 27(14), 9927-9940.
- 2) Droby, A., Thaler, A., & Mirelman, A. (2023). Imaging Markers in Genetic Forms of Parkinson's Disease. *Brain Sciences*, 13(8), 1212.
- 3) Qodarul, M. R., Silvia, L., Zainuri, M., & Dwihapsari, Y. (2023, May). The effect of repetition time variation on quantitative T1 magnetic resonance imaging on Agar. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2604, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
- 4) Aldawsari, A. M., Al-Qaisieh, B., Broadbent, D. A., Bird, D., Murray, L., & Speight, R. (2023). The role and potential of using quantitative MRI biomarkers for imaging guidance in brain cancer radiotherapy treatment planning: A systematic review. *Physics and Imaging in Radiation Oncology*, 100476.
- 5) Zhu, Z. (2023). Application of magnetic resonance imaging technology in the diagnosis of brain diseases. *Advances in Engineering Technology Research*, 6(1), 563-563.
- 6) Makita, N., Ishii, R., Yamaguchi, Y., Nakamura, Y., Miwa, K., Yoshimura, S., ... & Koga, M. (2023). Recurrence of intracranial artery dissection more than a half year after the initial event. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences*, 120716.
- 7) Hsia, C. C. (2023, August). Tissue Perfusion and Diffusion and Cellular Respiration: Transport and Utilization of Oxygen. In *Seminars in Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. 333 Seventh Avenue, 18th Floor, New York, NY 10001, USA: Thieme Medical Publishers, Inc.
- 8) Liu, Z. (Ed.). (2023). *Visualized Medicine: Emerging Techniques and Developing Frontiers*.
- 9) Khalili, N., Wang, R., Garg, T., Ahmed, A., Hoseinyazdi, M., Sair, H. I., ... & Yedavalli, V. (2023). Clinical application of brain perfusion imaging in detecting stroke mimics: A review. *Journal of Neuroimaging*, 33(1), 44-57.
- 10) Hnilicova, P., Kantorova, E., Sutovsky, S., Grofik, M., Zelenak, K., Kurca, E., ... & Kolisek, M. (2023). Imaging Methods Applicable in Diagnosing Alzheimer's Disease, Considering the Involvement of Insulin Resistance. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(4), 3325.

- 11) Perez, R. C., Kim, D., Maxwell, A. W., & Camacho, J. C. (2023). Functional Imaging of Hypoxia: PET and MRI. *Cancers*, 15(13), 3336.
- 12) Wettervik, T. S., Fahlström, M., Wikström, J., Lewén, A., & Enblad, P. (2023). Cerebrovascular reserve in Moyamoya disease: relation to cerebral blood flow, capillary dysfunction, oxygenation, and energy metabolism. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 14.
- 13) Islam, S., Inglese, M., Grech-Sollars, M., Aravind, P., Dubash, S., Barwick, T. D., ... & Aboagye, E. O. (2023). Feasibility of [18F] fluoropivalate hybrid PET/MRI for imaging lower and higher grade glioma: a prospective first-in-patient pilot study. *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging*, 1-14
- 14) Agrawal, P., Wilkstein, K., Guinn, E., Mason, M., Serrano Martinez, C. I., & Saylae, J. (2023). A Review of Tangential Flow Filtration: Process Development and Applications in the Pharmaceutical Industry. *Organic Process Research & Development*, 27(4), 571-591.
- 15) Prabhu, S. R. (2023). Dental, Oral, Maxillofacial and Salivary Gland Diseases: An Overview. *Textbook of General Pathology for Dental Students*, 123-131.
- 16) Dias, L. M. R. (2023). *Shifting Networks in Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): Brain network properties derived comparing resting state versus passive viewing* (Doctoral dissertation).
- 17) Zhu, Z. (2023). Application of magnetic resonance imaging technology in the diagnosis of brain diseases. *Advances in Engineering Technology Research*, 6(1), 563-563.
- 18) Anand, T., Ishaque, A., Ta, D., Khan, M. U., Bharti, K., Wu, A., ... & Kalra, S. (2023). Characterization of white matter alterations using diffusion kurtosis imaging in patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Brain and Behavior*, e3102.
- 19) Poirier, S. E., Suskin, N. G., Khaw, A. V., Thiessen, J. D., Shoemaker, J. K., & Anazodo, U. C. (2023). Probing evidence of cerebral white matter microstructural disruptions in ischemic heart disease before and following cardiac rehabilitation: A diffusion tensor MR imaging study. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*.